

Grant Agreement number: 101095017

Project acronym: COOPERATE

Project coordinator: TU/e

Project title: COOrdinating and Piloting actions towards ERA-hubs as inTer- and intra-regional Ecosystems for knowledge production

Deliverable D4.2 – “Call for Champions” Toolkit

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN

CESKE VYSOKE UCENI TECHNICKE V PRAZE

STAM

BRAINPORT DEVELOPMENT NV

SCIENCE CITY LYNGBY

DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET

IDEA STRATEGISCHE ECONOMISCHE CONSULTING

WP4 - Piloting and Monitoring the ERA-Hub Model Testing

WP leader – IDEA

PROJECT TITLE**COORDINATING AND PILOTING ACTIONS TOWARDS ERA-HUBS AS INTER- AND INTRA-REGIONAL ECOSYSTEMS FOR KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION**

PROJECT NUMBER	101095017
PROJECT ACRONYM	COOPERATE
GA NUMBER	101095017
PROJECT COORDINATOR	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN (TU/e)
PROJECT DURATION	30 months
DELIVERABLE NUMBER	D4.2
DELIVERABLE TITLE	"Call for Champions" Toolkit
DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION	Call for Champions toolkit
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	PU-Public
WORK PACKAGE NUMBER	WP4
LEAD BENEFICIARY	STAM
DELIVERABLE DUE DATE	30/04/2025
SUBMISSION DATE	30/04/2025
SUBMISSION VERSION	V2.0

Table of Contents

<i>List of Pictures</i>	3
<i>List of Tables</i>	3
<i>List of Figures</i>	3
<i>Executive Summary</i>	4
<i>List of abbreviation/Nomenclature</i>	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Context of Call for Champions	7
2.1 Evaluation procedure	9
3 Communication toolkit	11
4 KPIs of the Call for Champions	15
5 Conclusion	17

List of Pictures

Picture 1 - Ecosystem Readiness Level.....	8
Picture 2 - Text of the Call for Champions	12
Picture 3 - Example of a social media post	13
Picture 4 - Example of presentation (joint events)	14
Picture 5 - Example of presentation (webinar).....	15
Picture 6 - KPIs of the Call for Champions.....	15

List of Tables

Table 1 - Classification of ecosystems	8
Table 2 - Eligibility criteria	10
Table 3 - Evaluation criteria	10
Table 4 - Registered participants to the webinar	16
Table 5 - Registered participants to the explanatory meetings	16

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Building blocks of the Call for Champions	7
Figure 2 - Call for Champions and piloting phases	8

Executive Summary

The Call for Champions marks a key transition in the COOPERATE Project, moving from Piloting Phase I to Phase II, with the aim of validating and refining the ERA Hub model. The CALL is designed to select two emerging ecosystems to participate in Phase II, building insights from the first piloting phase and co-creation sessions that helped define the ERA Hub.

This initiative is part of the project's inverted funnel approach and contributes to the hands-on co-creation process with the extended Co-Design Task Force (CDTF). Additionally, the CALL supports the Communication and Outreach Strategy (see Deliverable 5.4 “Communication and Outreach Strategy”), facilitating the transfer of project results to a targeted stakeholder group. The selected ecosystems will play a vital role in testing and evaluating these results.

Overall, this Deliverable 4.2 provides an overview of how the CALL has been conceptualized, drafted and managed; while emphasizing its synergies with Work Package 5, with special regard on how the CALL has been communicated and disseminated.

List of abbreviation/Nomenclature

ACRONYM	STANDS FOR
CALL	Call For Champions
D	Deliverable
DX.X	Deliverable Number
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
ERL	Ecosystem Readiness Level
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MA	Maturity Assessment
PLAYBOOK	COOPERATE Playbook
R&I	Research and Innovation
SA	Self-Assessment
TOOLBOX	COOPERATE Toolbox
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The Call for Champions (CALL) represents an opportunity both for the project partners and for applicants to actively contribute to the whole process of testing and validating the ERA Hub concept and the other outputs of the project (for example, the COOPERATE Toolbox and COOPERATE Self-Assessment Digital Tool). Hence, the objective of the CALL is to select two emerging ecosystems to engage in the Piloting Phase II, which is meant to validate the model while also refining it.

From a broad perspective, the CALL builds on the takeaways of the first Piloting Phase, together with policies' research and analysis, and the co-creation sessions. Hence, following the COOPERATE "Guidelines and planning for co-creation activities, and establishment of the CDTF"¹, the Call for Champions plays a role in the inverted funnel approach as it represents one of the three "hands-on co-creation arenas" in the co-creation phase with the extended Co-Design Task Force (CDTF).

Yet, if on the one hand, the CALL concretises the initial results of Phase I Piloting and the definition of ERA Hub; on the other, it equally contributes to foster and implement the "Communication and Outreach Strategy"². It supports an initial transfer of the results of the project, it targets a specific stakeholder group, while actively involving new stakeholders in the project as also envisioned in the outreach process.

Based on the above-mentioned, this deliverable collects the main communication actions and tools in the so-called "Toolkit" (Section 3); while providing an overview on the content of the CALL in Section 1 and Section 2. Finally, Section 4 summarises the main KPIs, and the actions implemented in this regard. Overall, the entire deliverable has been structured from a more communicative and/or disseminating perspective, highlighting the synergies with the Work Package 5.

This document has been written by STAM, revised by Brainport Development, approved by IDEA Consult.

¹ For further details please consult: COOPERATE Project "Guidelines and planning for co-creation activities, and establishment of the CDTF"

² For further details please consult: COOPERATE Deliverable D.5.4 "Communication and Outreach Strategy"

2 Context of Call for Champions

The Call for Champions merges together the theoretical progresses and results from the co-creation activities (WP1) with those of the Piloting Phase I (WP4); using them as a framework to position the COOPERATE Project in the ERA context and to address a specific target audience (WP5).

Figure 1 - Building blocks of the Call for Champions

The building blocks taken from WP1 were the policy analysis, the ERA Hub definition (developed by September-October 2024), as well as the feedback collected through the series of co-creation sessions³. The co-creation activities were especially paramount in supporting the COOPERATE Consortium in progressing with the ERA Hub definition; in drafting the eligibility criteria as well as the evaluation ones. Based on the definition developed by the COOPERATE Consortium⁴, an ERA Hub acts as a driving force in the quadruple helix interaction, promoting interregional excellence by encouraging knowledge valorisation, as well as fostering collaboration and learning both within and

across regions. According to the definition, the central access points can be Technology Transfer Offices (TTOs), Knowledge Transfer Offices (KTOs), and universities. The latter play a key role in Research and Innovation ecosystems, by facilitating the exchange of knowledge among the quadruple helix actors, benefitting from their ability to serve as orchestrators. In addition, according to the COOPERATE Project, the ecosystems have been classified into four different groups (non-existent, emerging, mature or advanced), each representing a different level of maturity in terms of interaction and coordination among quadruple helix actors. This aspect is of crucial importance as the CALL specifically targets the emerging ecosystems. Drawing inspiration from “Local Ecosystem Readiness Levels” and “Technology Readiness Levels,” (TRL) the ERA Hub model introduced by the Project defines maturity through an "Ecosystem Readiness Level" scale (see [Picture 1](#)), and the types of ecosystems as outlined in [Table 1](#).

³ For further details please consult: COOPERATE Deliverable D1.1 – Initial ERA Hub Framework and KPIs; COOPERATE Deliverable D1.2 – Report on Co-creation with CDTF

⁴ Definition of ERA Hub “An ERA Hub is a central access point that stimulates the knowledge flow among quadruple helix actors to foster excellent and sustainable place-based R&I ecosystems. It provides a range of services to accelerate knowledge valorisation and to improve interregional collaboration”.

Non-existent	Emerging	Mature	Advanced
There is no or little interaction between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation	There is some interaction between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation but the coordination and development of joint activities is limited and requires further development.	There is interaction and coordination between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation in the delivery of joint activities but there are major points requiring improvement	There is fluid interaction and coordination between the local actors involved in knowledge production, transfer and exploitation in the delivery of joint activities

Table 1 - Classification of ecosystems

Picture 1 - Ecosystem Readiness Level

The theoretical framework of WP1 was further integrated with the results of the first Piloting Phase (part of WP4), which, as also reported in [Figure 2](#), took place with the ecosystems represented in the project Consortium, namely Danish, Dutch and Czech. Hence, those primary results served as guidance

Figure 2 - Call for Champions and piloting phases

in defining the benefits that the two selected emerging R&I ecosystems would profit from. In fact, the mutual exchange with different stakeholders, allowed the project partners to better understand what the expectations and needs of the R&I ecosystems around the topic of ERA Hub are. From this it followed that, besides the support and guidance provided by the COOPERATE Consortium for the two selected

ecosystems, the latter will also benefit from the direct involvement in the exchanges around the ERA Hubs concept in future EU policy (e.g. future European Commission’s R&I Framework Programme). Moreover, being engaged within a European project increases their networking opportunities with other EU ecosystems and R&I stakeholders through the co-creation sessions. Similarly, visibility at European level and within the ERA community represents another benefit for the two selected ecosystems.

As shown in [Figure 1](#) above, the Call for Champions can also be considered a cross-cutting exercise, encompassing different Work Packages: it is encapsulated within WP4 on “Piloting and Monitoring the ERA-Hub Model Testing”, while deriving some key concepts from WP 1 “Co-design the ERA Hub model and KPI” and fostering Work Package 5 “Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Activities” and the impact maximization.

Therefore, one final aspect to consider regarding the context of the CALL is communication. Thus, to assure a clear and transparent procedure, while transmitting the rationale of the CALL, the latter was structured into different sections, allowing the applicants to:

- Grasp the main objective of the COOPERATE project
- Understand the scope of the CALL
- Be aware of the eligibility criteria
- Examine the evaluation criteria and related scoring system

In addition, with the intent of supporting applicants, a dedicated “Help Desk” was created and operating for the whole duration of the CALL. The “Help Desk”, developed with the support of WP5, consisted of an email address, available on the application form, through which potential applicants could transmit specific requests. A Q&A section was available on the project website, favouring, once again, the clear communication and the application procedure. To provide a practical example of how transparency was assured, the next session reports more in detail the evaluation procedure.

2.1 Evaluation procedure

To ensure transparency throughout the entire Call for Champions process, the evaluation procedure and criteria were clearly outlined in the text of the CALL. Therefore, in addition to meeting the standard requirements expected of any open call, having a clear and transparent evaluation process was also deemed essential to be in line with the whole communication strategy of the COOPERATE Project, particularly under section “4.1 Segmentation of Audiences for Tailored Communication” of the Deliverable 5.4 of the “Communication and Outreach Strategy”⁵. Besides, transparency was also assured through a clear communication, benefitting from the insights and inputs of the Deliverable 5.4 of the “Communication and Outreach Strategy”⁶.

Following the above-mentioned, the CALL was organised as a well-structured and linear text, with a dedicated section specifically addressing the evaluation procedure. The usage of tables also eases the transparency of the process, while distinctly highlighting the requirements and criteria. Overall, these considerations fostered transparency, avoiding miscommunication and/or unfairness.

All applications submitted via the dedicated email address within the specified deadline were collected and assessed against the established eligibility criteria (see [Table 2](#)).

⁵ For further details please consult: COOPERATE Deliverable D.5.4 “Communication and Outreach Strategy”

⁶ For further details please consult: COOPERATE Deliverable D.5.4 “Communication and Outreach Strategy”

Be established in one of the eligible countries	☑
Be a university or an organisation with close links with it and active in the field of knowledge valorisation: such as Knowledge Transfer Organisations (KTO), Technology Transfer Offices (TTO), university-based incubators.	☑
Be part of an emerging ecosystem	☑

Table 2 - Eligibility criteria

If no errors or inconsistencies were found, the proposal moved on to the evaluation phase, following the evaluation criteria, as listed in [Table 3](#).

Shows interest from quadruple helix actors to participate in the piloting activities	1-5 points
Has proven track record of actions in the field of knowledge valorisation	1-5 points
Has proven track record of actions on the seven lines of actions	1-5 points
Shows credible potential for maturity growth	1-5 points

Table 3 - Evaluation criteria

To assure geographical balance and coverage, in case of a tie in rankings, the following parameters applied:

- If the tied applications are the top two, both will be selected (as far as they do not refer to the same country/region).
- If the tied applications are ranked second, the one geographically further from the first one ranked will be selected.

Three members of the Evaluation Committee (EV) reviewed the submitted proposals. Each member recorded its evaluation results in a shared database, to compare the ratings given by different EV members. The EV then reviewed all evaluations in the database and ranked the applications accordingly. The entire evaluation process was carried out by three COOPERATE partners during the month of December. Evaluations were sent at the beginning of January to each participant, with a detailed explanation and comments (under the section “evaluation explanation”) on all the different sections of the application and the overall score achieved out of 20.

Finally, the four applications referred to ecosystems located in Croatia, Finland, France and Poland. The final ranking was the following:

1. University of Lodz
2. University of Orléans
3. University of Rijeka
4. Metropolia University of Applied Sciences

No appeals followed the evaluations suggesting that both the application procedure and evaluation procedures were clear and transparent enough for applicants.

3 Communication toolkit

As mentioned in the Grant Agreement, a dedicated Toolkit has been elaborated and shared with partners involved in the communication and dissemination activities (WP5). Most of the exchange took place with Brainport Development, leading partner of WP5.

As the Call for Champions was made publicly available and actions were taken to boost its visibility; it was paramount to have a coordinated and structured communication among WPs. Hence, among the three objectives of the “Communication and Outreach Strategy”⁷, the CALL contributed to:

1. raising awareness around the project and its mission (Obj.1)
2. favouring the project positioning among other initiatives (Obj.2)
3. reaching target groups that can adapt and localise in their ecosystems the outputs of the project (Obj.3)

Equally, the CALL marked a concrete step in implementing the engagement of stakeholders and outreach process, as the two selected ecosystems will be fully engaged in the Piloting Phase II, proactively contributing to the implementation of the whole project.

Considering the above-mentioned, a set of outputs were developed and included in the so-called “communication toolkit”, which consists of documents, visuals, presentations targeting the CALL, its implementation and dissemination. Therefore, the toolkit includes:

- Documents for the Call for Champions
 - Text of the Call for Champions and Annexes
 - Q&A leaflet
- Draft invitation for stakeholders to apply to the CALL
- Draft text and visual for social media (LinkedIn)
- Events presentations
- Press Release

Following the “Communication and Outreach Strategy”⁸, the CALL reported: the COOPERATE logo; the Project number: 101095017; and the EU flag including text to acknowledge the support under Horizon Europe. Furthermore, with the intention to channel all the information of the project in a single access point, the Call for Champions has been published on the official project website and highlighted as “focus” topic in the homepage. This action was taken to foster the visibility of the call, while allowing the applicants to further navigate into the project if in need of more information. In addition, a dedicated page on the website provided all the relevant information for the application, as well as the Q&A leaflet.

The text of the CALL was designed in a structured matter guiding the applicants through the main

⁷ For further details please consult: COOPERATE Deliverable D.5.4 “Communication and Outreach Strategy”

⁸ For further details please consult: COOPERATE Deliverable D.5.4 “Communication and Outreach Strategy”

aspects of it. Hence, the text reported the key features of the concept of ERA Hub (WP1), setting the scene for the understanding of the CALL; while being schematized and subdivided into paragraphs, easing the comprehension of the eligibility criteria and the evaluation criteria. As the ERA Hub concepts builds on other concepts, be they “quadruple helix” and “knowledge valorisation”, the CALL included a glossary to specify their meanings, while also providing references to European policies within which the ERA framework is incapsulated. Picture 2 below reports the first two pages of the text of the CALL, providing references to the specific details which follow the communication strategy: from fonts and colours to communication and project identity.

Picture 2 - Text of the Call for Champions

Consistency in the dissemination actions is marked also in other two means of communication: social media and presentations, which also symbolise different ways of communicating. Starting with social media, they require visuals that can attract the audience, catching the attention; together with a short, easy to understand text which directly points at the main object.

Moreover, as COOPERATE Project uses mainly LinkedIn, the post should also be more “business” oriented, using hashtags to highlighted main topics, spread the message and being associated with similar contents (see Picture 3 below).

COOPERATE
339 followers
4mo

Webinar: Call for Champions

With great pleasure we share one of the latest initiatives developed within the project: the "Call for Champions". The latter is meant to identify two emerging ecosystems, which will benefit from:

- Support and guidance in their progress as ecosystem
- Involvement in the reflections to define and apply the ERA-Hubs concept in future EU policy.
- Networking opportunities within their regions as well as with other EU **#ecosystems** and R&I stakeholders through the co-creation sessions.
- Increased visibility at European level and within the **#ERA** community

If you are interested to know more on the "Call for Champions" join the **#webinar** on **Thursday 10th October 2024 | 09.00-10.00 AM CET on Teams Platform**. We will present you the "Call for Champions", while explaining the application procedures. There will be time for a Q&A session to clarify your doubts and questions!

Register here: <https://lnkd.in/ehZRvtQ!>

COOPERATE

WEBINAR

Call for R&I ecosystems

Thursday, 10th October 2024
09.00-10.00 AM CET

Ready to know more on the "Call for Champions"?

- Application procedure
- Benefits of the call
- Q&A Session

REGISTER

www.cooperate-project.eu

Callouts:

- One key message
- Target audience
- Hashtags
- Key information highlighted
- Project logo
- Clear visual
- Reference of the project

Picture 3 - Example of a social media post

Regarding presentations, these are also valuable communication tools which were equally used – and thus included in the Toolkit – during the CALL. Slightly differently from the LinkedIn posts, presentations mainly serve as support to the speakers, therefore they normally do not present much of text. In fact, the will is to catch the attention of the audience by explaining the main objective, rather than having it available to read. In addition, as it was also the case for a public event, a “call to action” – meaning something that the audience can do to proactively be involved – was also added to the slide. One example is the QR Code in [Picture 4](#). This action is particularly relevant especially when there are different speakers present at one event, as it allows the audience to access additional materials, information and/or remain updated with the projects (e.g. the “call to action” is related to a social media channel). Nonetheless, whether it is a joint public event or a registration-based webinar, the key features of the communication strategies were present. [Picture 5](#) shows an example of a slide presented during the “Call for Champions: presentation webinar”, highlighting the communication features.

Picture 4 - Example of presentation (joint events)

Picture 5 - Example of presentation (webinar)

4 KPIs of the Call for Champions

The Call for Champions actively contributes to the development of the ERA Hub network, while attracting stakeholders from different R&I ecosystems. At the same time, considering the horizontality of this activity as mentioned in the previous section, the CALL favoured the expansion of the action of the COOPERATE Project involving two new emerging ecosystems for the Piloting Phase II and validation of the ERA Hub Model. Picture 6 summarizes the indicators to meet in regard to the CALL.

<p>Launch of Call for Champions</p>	<p>At least 15 regional ecosystems register to the launch webinar and at least 6 ecosystems apply to the call fulfilling basic compliance requirements based on the ERA Hub model set in WP1 to finally select 2 ecosystems based on detailed criteria to be defined (Obj. 3) and ensuring geographical distribution across EU.</p>
-------------------------------------	--

Picture 6 - KPIs of the Call for Champions

The official launch of the Call for Champions took place in Brussels, on September 19th, 2024, during the event co-organized with ERA Fabric, following the Inspiring ERA Event. Titled “European Research Area: Fostering Greater Integration. Advancing Competitiveness. *ERA Hubs: status and way forward*”, the event was structured to integrate COOPERATE and ERA Fabric insights, results and reflections to the audience and discuss with them possible way forward. With this occasion, the Call for Champions was publicly explained and launched, together with the explanatory webinar. The latter served as a dedicated moment to give an explanation on the CALL application procedure, the criteria and benefits. The webinar took place on Thursday 10th October 2024, from 09.00 to 10.00 AM CET on Teams Platform, and 18 people registered from different organizations as per Table 4 below.

N. of participants	Organisation	Country	Registered to the webinar
1	Region of Murcia Brussels Office	Spain	Yes
1	Tecnopolis PST	Italy	Yes
1	Universidad de Cádiz	Spain	Yes
1	Warsaw University of Technology	Poland	Yes
1	Brandenburg University of Technology	Germany	Yes
1	Politehnica University Timisoara	Romania	Yes
1	West University of Timisoara	Romania	Yes
1	Medical University of Gdansk - Technology Transfer Office	Poland	Yes
3	Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv	Ukraine	Yes
2	West Finland European Office	Finland	Yes
1	Independent/MCAA	Austria	Yes
1	University of Malta	Malta	Yes
1	Breda University of Applied Sciences	Netherlands	Yes
1	University of Lodz	Poland	Yes
1	MAD emergent art center	Netherlands	Yes

Table 4 - Registered participants to the webinar

Please note that considering the expression of interest of other potential applicants, which were not able to join the webinar on 10th October, two other explanatory meetings were held (see [Table 5](#) for further details).

N. of participants	Organisation	Country	Date of the meeting
2	Solutions-eco	France	9/10/2024
3	Pays de la Loire	France	9/10/2024
1	ADR Nord-Est	Romania	15/10/2024

Table 5 - Registered participants to the explanatory meetings

This flexibility of the COOPERATE Consortium allowed the overall participation of 24 people, covering 18 different organisations and 10 countries, going beyond the target indicator of 15 registrations while ensuring geographical distribution.

The other indicator to meet referred to the number of applications, whereby 6 applications were targeted. Considering the challenges in receiving applications to meet the minimum number required (6), the COOPERATE partners applied the actions listed in Part A of the Grant Agreement (p.22) to mitigate this risk, while taking further actions to incentive the applications. More in depth six actions were put in place:

- ✓ Specific explanatory meetings besides the foreseen webinar were organised
- ✓ The deadline of the Call for Champions was postponed to the end of November (initial deadline end of October), allowing more time for the application
- ✓ Visibility to the CALL was given during the even in Brussels, addressing key stakeholders

- ✓ A dedicated newsletter was shared among the subscribers
- ✓ Specific posts were done on LinkedIn subscribers (e.g. see [Picture 3](#) - Example of a social media post)
- ✓ Extra mobilisation of partners' network was carried out

Finally, only 4 applications were received. Considering the above-mentioned mitigation actions, the evaluation procedure took place, leading to the selection of two emerging ecosystems out of the four applying ones. The two selected ecosystems also ensured the geographical distribution across the EU, satisfying the targeted outcome of the KPI.

5 Conclusion

The Call for Champions marks a pivotal step in the progression of the COOPERATE Project, acting as both a bridge and a catalyst between the conceptual development of the ERA Hub and its practical implementation. By selecting two emerging ecosystems to participate in Piloting Phase II, the CALL aims to validate ERA Hub model, leveraging the insights gained from the first piloting phase, the policy research carried out in WP1, and a series of co-creation activities. In addition, the CALL aligns closely with the goals of the Communication and Outreach Strategy (WP5): it facilitates the dissemination of project outcomes to a targeted yet expanding group of stakeholders while ensuring active participation in shaping the next stages of the initiative. Moreover, the CALL illustrates the practical application of the ERA Hub's definition, fostering collaboration across the quadruple helix actors—universities, public institutions, industry, and civil society.

Besides, the CALL is not only essential for testing the robustness and applicability of the tools developed—such as the COOPERATE Toolbox and Self-Assessment Digital Tool—but also for deepening stakeholder engagement and strengthening the foundation of the broader ERA ecosystem.

Ultimately, the Call for Champions showcases how theoretical progress, and practical implementation can converge to accelerate innovation and support ecosystems in their path within the ERA Hub process.